

MS13

Dataset of the results of the deliberative choice experi- ments

Lead Beneficiary: 12 - James Hutton Institute
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Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** October 31st, 2024
- **Actual submission date:** October 25th, 2024
- **Project start date:** September 1st, 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP5
- **Work package leader:** Bálint Bálazs
- **Milestone Title:** "Dataset of the results of the deliberative choice experiments"

- **Mean of Verification**

The collection of the results of the deliberative choice experiments will be finalised.

1. Milestone description

Milestone 13 is based on the activities undertaken within Task 5.3 “Farmers’ and consumers’ expectations and preferences for UCs”, under the leadership of The James Hutton Institute and with the support of local partners. T5.3 aimed at assessing consumers’ and farmers’ preferences with respect to five underutilised crops (UCs) from different pedoclimatic zones, by conducting choice experiments (consumers) and deliberative choice experiments (farmers) within focus groups organised as part of CREATOR workshops. Below, we list the UCs selected (and the deriving food product where relevant), the country, the date of the CREATOR workshops, and the sample sizes achieved (farmers and consumers).

- 1) **Bere barley** (farmers) and **Bere flour** (consumers) – CREATOR workshop “Bere event”, held on 11-12 July 2022 in Kirkwall, Orkney Islands (**Scotland**), in collaboration with University of Highlands and Islands (UHI). Participants: 11 farmers (4 during the workshop, 7 online afterwards), for a total of 11 responses before discussion and 4 responses after discussion;¹ 11 consumers.
- 2) **Tomaca de Penjar de Benlloc** (farmers and consumers) – CREATOR workshop “Woody crops event programme”, held on 16-18 February 2023 in Castellón, Valencian Region (**Spain**), in collaboration with Connecta Natura NGO (CONAT). Participants: 19 farmers (14 during the workshop, 5 online afterwards), for a total of 19 responses before discussion and 11 responses after discussion; 17 consumers.
- 3) **IDEAL tomato** (farmers and consumers) – CREATOR workshop “Traditional tomato”, held on 5-6 October 2023 in Plovdiv (**Bulgaria**), in collaboration with Institute of Agrostrategies and Innovations (IAI). Participants: 21 farmers (9 during the workshop, 12 online afterwards), for a total of 21 responses before discussion and 9 responses after discussion; 22 consumers.²

¹ The number of responses after discussion can differ from the number of workshop participants because some farmers proceeded to the second part of the questionnaire despite the instructions to wait.

² Until the Bulgarian workshop, the number of “choice cards” per respondent was 9 (i.e., the total number of choices is nine times the number of respondents). This was reduced to 6 afterwards, following participants’ feedback according to which the cards were too many.

- 4) **Yellow pea** (farmers) and **pasta** using yellow pea protein (consumers) – CREATOR workshop “Dynamic value chain in action! Yellow pea and beyond”, held on 16-17 May 2024 in Melfi, Potenza Province (**Italy**), in collaboration with HiWeiss SRL (HiW). Participants: 18 farmers (14 during the workshop, 4 online afterwards), for a total of 18 responses before discussion and 13 responses after discussion; 19 consumers.
- 5) **Mixes of underutilised gramineous and leguminous crops** to be used as feed for cows (farmers) and **Parmigiano Reggiano** cheese (consumers) – CREATOR workshop “Underutilised crops in the Parmigiano Reggiano value chain”, held on 19-20 September 2024 in Reggio-Emilia and Casina, Reggio-Emilia Province (**Italy**), in collaboration with Centro Ricerche Produzioni Animali (CRPA). Participants: 21 farmers (19 during the workshop, 2 online afterwards), for a total of 21 responses before discussion and 18 responses after discussion; 21 consumers.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

The datasets are securely stored in the drives of The James Hutton Institute as well as in the Basecamp repository at <https://3.basecamp.com/5014875/buckets/21627509/vaults/7887224045>. They will be prepared for open access publication (with embargo) in an online repository, e.g. Zenodo, before the end of the RADIANT project. Preliminary analyses of choice data have been conducted after each CREATOR workshop, and the results are presented, alongside an overview of the activities conducted, in the respective reports, available in the RADIANT website at <https://www.radiantproject.eu/reports/>.³

³ An exception is represented by the Reggio-Emilia workshop, for which, due to the recent finalisation, the preparation of the report is ongoing.

